

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER AND THE TEACHING METHODS FOR SPEAKING SKILLS

Zakirova Dilorom Yuldashevna

Senior teacher, Department of Foreign Languages, Tashkent Institute of Finance

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7192662>

Abstract. *The article is about problem of improving the efficiency of teaching oral speech oral speech in foreign language classes is discussed in the article. This issue is directly related to the disconnect between theory and practice and the passive nature of learning activities, whereas the educated active person who is capable of ongoing self-education, self-development, and self-improvement becomes the ultimate value of society. In this paper, I'd want to discuss the teacher's interactions with students in a foreign language during class time and after school, student interactions with teachers during class time, and student interactions with teachers during extracurricular activities.*

Keywords: *speaking, abilities, skill, exercise system, activities, oral speech, development, grammar, communicative, approach, individuality, motivation, task, formation.*

РОЛЬ УЧИТЕЛЯ И МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НАВЫКАМ ГОВОРЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается проблема повышения эффективности обучения устной речи устной речи на занятиях по иностранному языку. Этот вопрос напрямую связан с несоответствием теории и практики и пассивным характером учебной деятельности, тогда как высшей ценностью общества становится образованный активный человек, способный к постоянному самообразованию, саморазвитию и самосовершенствованию. В этой статье я хотел бы обсудить взаимодействие учителя с учениками на иностранном языке во время урока и после школы, взаимодействие ученика с учителем во время урока и взаимодействие ученика с учителем во время внеклассной деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *говорение, умения, умение, система упражнений, деятельность, устная речь, развитие, грамматика, коммуникативность, подход, индивидуальность, мотивация, задача, формирование.*

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, communicative competence has become a priority in teaching a foreign language. It is important to teach students to speak fluent English in order to communicate freely with English-speaking interlocutors. Not easy to achieve communication. The teacher teaches not only the phonetic pronunciation of words and phrases, grammar, and intonation features, but also how and when it is better to say something that is said in one or another case. Real communication is also facial expressions, smile, stress, and gestures. And here we cannot do without the rules of conversation, without the knowledge of the culture of the country whose language they are learning. Receiving information about culture, students form an attitude towards this culture, and hence the motivation to learn a language. The task is difficult, and you need to start solving it from the initial stage of learning. At the initial stage, great attention is paid to listening, phonetic refinement, repeated repetition of both words and grammatical structures.

Although the language experience is still small, it is nevertheless necessary to direct the work to the ability to communicate in a foreign language. It is important to identify a system of

exercises for the development of skills of unprepared speech, since these exercises will be used in the future, but at a more difficult level.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Training goes on specific topics. Students are involved in a wide variety of activities. The language itself, language training of structures is hidden behind the interesting content of the topic. Words and sentences become clear precisely because of the context. Topics must be in the interests of students. This helps to increase motivation, and therefore it is useful to use additional CMDs. In the system of exercises aimed at the development of oral speech, I want to highlight the game, since in it the abilities of the child are especially complete and unexpectedly manifest. The game always involves making a decision, and the desire to decide sharpens the mental activity of the players. The game contributes to the implementation of important methodological tasks. Firstly, it creates psychological readiness for speech communication. When learning to speak, it is necessary to develop cognitive abilities. Language competence is most often disclosed as a set of specific skills that we need for speech contacts and language acquisition as an academic discipline. When we talk about communication, naturally, there are questions: for what reason do we communicate, with whom we communicate. Any of our activities contain motive, purpose, action and operations. As for the actions and operations in any lesson, then from the teacher's side, they are usually aimed at students mastering the knowledge and skills on the subject, and students often perform certain actions or tasks without thinking about their essence or benefits. In addition, many adolescent students have academic problems. Often this is due not to the child's performance or intellectual abilities, but to a sharp drop in interest in learning, a decrease in learning motivation. My task at all stages of teaching English is to support learning motivation: my task is to form students' sustainable motivation to succeed, to increase self-esteem. In my lessons, I pay great attention to the entertaining presentation, the emotionality of my speech, and cognitive games.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The teacher should try to come to the class only with a positively directed energy, speak kindly, be able to support the conversation on topics of interest to students, that is, know not only the basics of grammar, phonetics, vocabulary and country studies, but also understand at least a little in modern youth fashion, music, sports, literature, computer technology. As it is known, speaking is the way of verbal communication. The purpose of learning to speak at school is to develop the ability of students, in accordance with their real needs and interests, to carry out oral speech communication in a variety of situations. In order to facilitate communication among students, we must take into account the specific features of this type of speech activity, such as motivation, purposefulness, activity, connection with the personality and mental activity of a person, heuristic, autonomy, tempo and situationality. If there are goals and motives of communication, the characteristic features of the participants of communication, their age, level of development, etc., are taken into account, then the act of communication within a speech situation, of course, will take place.

CONCLUSION

To create these conditions in the process of learning the English language, I use activation techniques that take into account all the above listed signs of the oral speech activity. The advantages of these techniques are that students, actively participating in the learning process, begin to think about, recall, use the learned language material. Interactive role-playing games

and open discussions are related to creative tasks in the communicative method of teaching English. In my opinion, using them is a good way of activating high-school students to encourage them to speak verbally.

REFERENCES

1. Klippel, F.: *Keep Talking — Communicative Fluency Activities For Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1991
2. Brumfit, C. J., Johnson. *The Communicative Approach. To Language Teaching*. Oxford
3. Singhal, M. (1997). *The Internet and Foreign Language Education: Benefits and Challenges*. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 3(6), 1997.